

Potentiometric Studies in Solution of some Transitional Metal Ion and Rare Earth Metal Ion Complexes of 5-Benzal-3-methyl-2-thiohydantoin(5-benzal-3-methyl-4-imidozolinone-2-thioxo)[†]

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Manuscript received 26 December 1984, revised 26 June 1985, accepted 31 July 1985

The stepwise stability constants of complexes of 5-benzal-3-methyl-2-thiohydantoin with transition metal ions and rare earth metal ions are determined by Calvin-Bjerrum potentiometric titration method. The work is conducted in 3 : 1 (v/v) dioxane-water medium of ionic strength 0.1 *N* and at temperature 27 ± 1°. The order of stability constants is found to be in agreement with the order reported by earlier workers. In case of rare earth metal ions the stability constants observed are slightly lower as compared to the divalent metal ions studied, thereby indicating lesser ionic character.

THIOHYDANTOINS are heterocyclic 5-membered ring compounds used as analytical reagents for the estimation of transition metal ions. The compound has remarkable resistance towards hydrolysis. There is a tautomeric form through >C=S and the ionisation takes place from SH group. The ionisation has been proved by ir spectral analysis. The present investigation of stoichiometric metal-ligand stability constant of 5-benzal-3-methyl-2-thiohydantoin with divalent transition metal ions and rare earth metal ions is presented for the first time.

Experimental

The ligand 5-benzal-3-methyl-2-thiohydantoin was synthesised by standard method¹. The structure of the ligand was confirmed by ir spectral analysis. Dioxane was purified by the reported method². Distilled water, redistilled over KMnO₄ was used throughout the investigation.

The free acid, free acid plus ligand, and the mixture of metal containing the ligand and the acid were titrated against carbonate free sodium hydroxide (1*M*). The solutions of metal perchlorates were prepared from A.R. grade oxides or carbonates and standardised by EDTA titrations³. Potentiometric titrations were carried out in inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen-free nitrogen gas through the solution. All measurements were carried out at 27 ± 1° in dioxane-water (75 : 25, v/v) medium. Potentiometer readings were taken on a Toshniwal CL 46 digital pH meter with accuracy of ± 0.01 with combined glass-calomel electrodes.

Results and Discussion

\bar{n}_A values are obtained by using Irving and Rossotti equation and then *pK* value for the reagent is calculated. This value is confirmed by the plots of *B* vs \bar{n}_A , and *B* vs $\log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1-\bar{n}_A}$ (Fig. 1). The experimental readings are then used to calculate the value of \bar{n} (average number of ligand molecules

Fig. 1

[†] Paper presented at the 21st Annual Convention of Chemists and Diamond Jubilee Celebration of the Indian Chemical Society, Jadavpur University, Calcutta, October 14-19, 1984.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL-LIGAND COMPLEXES

Temp.	= 27 ± 1°							
$\mu = 0.1$								
Metal ion	H ⁺	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	Sm ^{III}	Gd ^{III}	Dy ^{III}
log k_1	11.05	9.1000	8.0000	4.9000	8.5500	7.9400	7.6400	7.4700
log k_n	—	6.4250	4.6550	3.4250	5.6500	—	—	—

attached per metal ion) and pL (free ligand exponents) applying Irving and Rossotti method⁴. The \bar{n} values are plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of metal complexation equilibria (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2

During the metal ion titration, the curves were displaced behind the reagent curve at lower pH

and emerged out at higher pH , indicating thereby the protonation at N_1 -atom in the heterocyclic ring and stepwise formation of complexes. Thus for the simplicity of calculations, new graphs are obtained by shifting the curves with equivalent amount of alkali required for the proton absorbed.

Limits of error and standard deviations for log K values are applied and most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of stability constants in case of transitional metals is found to be $Cu > Cd > Zn > Ni$. This order of stability is in agreement with the order reported earlier by many workers⁵⁻⁶. The values observed also indicate the increase in ionisation potential and reciprocal ionic radius on passing from Cd to Zn. The observed order, $Zn > Ni$ also supports the results of other workers⁷⁻⁹. The reversal of this order is attributed to steric factor. In case of rare earth metals the study was carried out to understand the bond character between rare earth metal ion and the ligand.

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